

Base4NFDI Publication Policy

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Purpose

This internal **publication policy** aims to ensure that research outputs from the Base4NFDI project are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) and sets out how the outputs of Base4NFDI should be published, stored, and referenced.

The outputs for Base4NFDI can be roughly categorised as project internal vs. external-facing outputs:

- The outputs of Base4NFDI, the Base4NFDI staff (which constitutes the Task Areas and the Service Stewards), and Co-Spokepersons, hereafter referred to as the “**Base4NFDI staff**”.
- The outputs of the flex funds-supported projects¹ in the Base4NFDI framework, hereafter referred to as the “**Basic service projects**”.

1. Publication Requirements

All publications, research data and other outputs produced within the Base4NFDI project must be made accessible. They can be divided into **published** and **non-published** content.

Also the Basic services teams are encouraged to follow the instructions below and to publish a selection of their deliverables on Zenodo and then list them on their respective web presence.

All publications must be assigned a persistent identifier that links to the full text and other metadata elements. Zenodo is recommended for this purpose and use of the ‘[Base4NFDI Zenodo community](#)’ is encouraged. As mentioned above, outputs should be published on Zenodo if it is deemed a publication and link to it from the Base4NFDI website.

¹ Flex funds explained in the Base4NFDI proposal: <https://zenodo.org/records/10245518>.

1.1 Published content: Open access and Peer-reviewed publications

The Base4NFDI staff publishes all publicly accessible guides, best practices, conference contributions, and reports under [CC-BY license](#) on Zenodo and / or on the Base4NFDI website.

All Base4NFDI-created peer-reviewed publications should be published in open access or deposited in a publication repository of their choice, either institutional or disciplinary. The published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in an online repository before, parallel to, or after the publication date. In some cases publishers require an embargo period before making the publication open access. Authorship should accurately reflect the contributions of those involved in the research. DFG and Base4NFDI funding acknowledgements should be indicated in the metadata (see section [Funding acknowledgement](#)).

1.2 Published content: Datasets

Any primary research data created related to the project by the Base4NFDI staff are expected to be shared with others in the Base4NFDI team and significant datasets and findings from research activities should be considered for publication.

It is up to the discretion of the Base4NFDI service teams to decide which of their outputs should be published on their web presence, submitted to Zenodo or in another appropriate data repository.

DFG funding should be acknowledged as mentioned below.

1.3 Survey results

Many service teams create surveys. Before a survey starts, the following should be mentioned in the data privacy policy notice:

“The data will be processed by the Basic service teams as well as the Base4NFDI staff.”

Respondents should be aware and informed that Base4NFDI will also have access to the raw data that could include personal data such as email addresses. Base4NFDI has developed survey guidance criteria for internal use. A survey documentation guide is available on the Base common storage platform.

If survey outputs are published, DFG funding should be acknowledged as mentioned below.

1.4 Reporting on Events, Conferences, Workshops

For the Base4NFDI staff: All Base4NFDI events where either a) Base4NFDI is being presented or b) Base4NFDI staff are attending or co-organising the event should be timely recorded in a work package in Open Project with a link to the original presentation in the common Base4NFDI storage platform and/or its published version on Zenodo or appropriate repository. The work package and/or the produced material should state if Base4NFDI was asked to present, what was expected, in which format, and who went to proceed with the task.

DFG funding and if appropriate the DFG and Base4NFDI logos should be acknowledged on the slides, poster or dissemination material.

1.5 Non-published outputs

Not all outputs need to be published: These should be stored as PDF in the common Base4NFDI storage drive, accessible to all and linked to the related Open Project work package.

Instructions for Zenodo

Select Base4NFDI Community. During upload, the Base4NFDI community can be selected. After the administrator has confirmed the publication, it appears in the community overview:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/base4nfdi>

Authorship should accurately reflect the contributions of those involved in the research, alphabetically. Note: Base4NFDI staff can be contributors to Basic service publications, but not authors.

If you need support, please contact us at base4nfdi-office@lists.nfdi.de.

2. Funding acknowledgements

DFG funding should be acknowledged in all published outputs.

1. **For Base4NFDI staff outputs:** The following DFGs numbers should be acknowledged on all outputs: 521453681, 521460392, 521462155, 521463400, 521466146, 521471126, 521473512, 521474032, 521475185, 521476232.
2. **Basic Service Teams:** All Base4NFDI services should acknowledge this DFG number: 521453681.

It is also possible to use the Base4NFDI and DFG logos, which are available for download on the website ([URL](#)).

3. Please add Funding metadata in Zenodo: The DFG can now also be selected as a funder. To do this, select 'Add Custom' under Funding in the metadata. In the following pop-up window, please select the 'Deutsche

Forschungsgemeinschaft' under the 'Funder' section. In the 'Additional information' section, please enter the relevant grant numbers (see above) in the 'Number' field.

Should you wish to add this information, you have the option to do so after publication.

3. Internal review process

For any staff still in the onboarding process (first six months) all public outputs (conference posters, presentations, abstracts) should be reviewed by two members of the Base4NFDI office and the relevant TA Co-Spokespersons before they are published or disseminated.

4. Templates for publishing

Standard templates exist for Base4NFDI presentations and posters ([URL](#)). Materials that document the deliverables of the Base4NFDI core team and the Basic service teams should use a Base4NFDI logo and a funding acknowledgement.

5. Base4NFDI website and Basic Service web presences

- [Instructions for Base4NFDI staff](#): The base4nfdi.de website shows events, publications, the Basic Services, and offers project teams to showcase their service at high-level (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects>). The website is operated by TA4 (office) and technically administered at TU Dresden using Joomla CMS

(status 12/2024). Abstracts of all the service applications are published on the Base4NFDI website <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/all-submissions>. Basic service teams are free to send high-level information to the office and the office regularly checks for updates on individual basic services' pages, or for the newest publications on Zenodo to include them on base4nfdi.de.

- **Instructions for Basic service teams:** Additionally, each Basic service project is expected to build their own web presence for the service (offerings). Base4NFDI offers two templates for setting the web presence up: [mkdocs](#) and [HuGo](#) (both on GitHub). Please refer to the existing website policy <https://zenodo.org/records/14245434> for info on what is expected from the basic service teams and what the Base4NFDI team provides in detail. For example, the policy lists requirements for e.g. service domain names, look and feel for our corporate identity, where to display funding information, and consults on legal information (privacy policy, imprint, accessibility). Moreover, each basic service team is provided with a privacy policy template that can be used for the web presence. This template is not published but sent separately. The policies and templates are continuously updated.

6. Documentation of Base4NFDI staff and service teams output

- **Open Project:** This is the principle management system used by all staff members of Base4NFDI **and** the Base4NFDI service teams. All activities should be tracked and outputs linked from the relevant OP area. All tasks, deliverables and milestones must be tracked here.
- **Minutes and agendas:** All TA meetings must be documented in English or German and stored in the common storage drive. Links to the relevant Open Project work packages are encouraged in all cases.

All outputs should be openly licensed under CC-BY.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Or an alternative open license with a clear license reflected.

Reproduced external material should be marked with the appropriate license.

Base4NFDI recommends to use the CC-BY license (this is the default in Zenodo). In some cases CC-BY ND is recommended, e.g. in the case of Audio Visual material.

Questions? Reach us any time at base4nfdi-office@lists.nfdi.de.

Appendix I. Template for Reporting

Presentation Request:

[Was Base4NFDI asked to present? (Yes/No)]

[Who made the request?]

Expectations:

[What was expected from the presentation? (e.g., topic, depth, key points), Specific requirements or constraints?]

Format:

[In which format was the presentation supposed to be delivered? (e.g., slides, workshop, talk, panel discussion)]

Responsibility & Execution:

[Who is responsible for proceeding with the task? Any required coordination with other teams or individuals?]